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AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY

USER GUIDE HANDBOOK

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Information in this handbook is subject to change

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Objectives of Handbook

This handbook is intended as a general introduction to the NERC Scientific Services (NSS) Airborne Remote Sensing Facility. The contents are mainly aimed at current and prospective users of the facility; to describe the aircraft platform and sensors, their capabilities, and to aid in the planning of airborne missions to derive the highest quality data for a particular application. Later sections are intended to cover the processing applied to the data, to produce radiometrically calibrated data products, and the geometric correction capability available to the user. An extensive Appendices are provided which contain details of the NERC ARS Facility and ancillary information on sensor characteristics and data format, useful for reference during image analysis and further processing by the user.

The handbook has been designed as a collection of self-contained sections which can be expanded or amended in future releases, as the ARS facility evolves. Feedback from users on mission planning criteria, novel analysis techniques or applications of the airborne data that should be included in later versions of the ARS Handbook are welcome.

2. NSS ARS SERVICE

2.1 Remit of NSS ARS

Within NERC Scientific Services (NSS) there is a group called Responsive Mode Services (RMS), which amongst its responsibilities in providing a wide range of support services, primarily to the higher education sector, is to manage the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARSF). The ARSF Mission Statement, included in Appendix A, lays down the main objectives of supporting environmental scientists by providing airborne remotely sensed data and in promoting awareness and application of airborne remote sensing techniques by dissemination to the wider scientific community. The Mission Statement also lists the means of achieving these objectives by provision of an airborne platform, equipped with a range of sensors, and by development and maintenance of a core of data processing software to deliver the quality and range of products to meet the user requirement. RMS also runs the Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (NERC-EPFS) which not only provides ground-based spectroradiometers to the user community, often for simultaneous ground measurements during overflights, but is involved in their intercalibration with the airborne sensors and in providing expertise on calibration, in general, for the ARSF.

2.2 ARSFSC & Peer Review System

An Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Steering Committee (ARSFSC) was established to provide advice to the Director NSS on aspects of the operations of the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility. The full terms of reference are also included in Appendix A, along with the current membership. One of the main duties of the steering committee is to review and grade, primarily on scientific merit, all research applications for use of the Facility. It also monitors the outputs of the Facility, user satisfaction with the service and advises on the direction of technical developments needed to meet the current and future user requirement.

2.3 AO for Research & CR

An Announcement of Opportunity (AO) is issued annually, to the academic and institute user community, in the year preceding the year for which the service is required. Full technical details of the sensors available, and guidance notes on the completion of the enclosed application form, are included with the AO. The applications, received by the due deadline, are reviewed by the ARSFSC and alpha graded proposals are then flown on an opportunistic basis, depending on the weather conditions and aircraft availability over a particular region. Airborne flights are coordinated by the ARS Operations Coordinator who liaises with the users

on exact timing, if required to be simultaneous with fieldwork, and on local weather conditions prior to over-flights. In addition to this standard route for access to airborne remotely sensed data, the user community may also, exceptionally, apply at any time of year for flights in response to transient phenomena such as floods and landslips or as a result of circumstances that could not be foreseen. The Facility may also be used to carry out Commissioned Research (CR) projects, wholly through NSS or via CR contracts held by NERC institute and university groups. A range of charges, based on the mix of internal research and external funding, can be arranged through the manager of the ARS Facility. These CR derived funds supplement income in order to provide the required level of service for the whole user community.

2.4 Brief History of the ARS Facility

NERC Scientific Services (NSS) has provided an Airborne Remote Sensing (ARS) service to the academic and institute research community since 1982 when it first hired in both aircraft and sensor instrumentation in support of Earth, terrestrial and freshwater, and marine sciences. This service has grown in response to the user community demand for access to timely, high quality and quantitative data using the latest range of optical sensors, beginning with the purchase of the current Piper Chieftain aircraft and subsequent conversion for survey work in 1983. In 1988 a Wild RC-8 camera was purchased to support the large photographic survey demand, for independent missions and in support of optical sensor operations. The growing demands for increased sensor availability culminated in 1993 with the purchase of the previously hired Daedalus 1268 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) scanner and purchase, in support of the NERC Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS) Community Programme, of an Itres Research Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) airborne imaging spectrometer. The photographic survey capability was upgraded in 1994 by purchase of a second-hand Wild RC-10 camera, providing more automated control. NSS are further enhancing the ARS Facility with the development of an integrated airborne system to synchronize data from the two imaging sensors with attitude and position information, provided by a multi-antennae Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS). A ground data processing system is also being set-up to provide the necessary quality control over radiometric calibration and provide airborne remotely sensed data as standard high quality products, geometrically correctable to a spatially referenced coordinate system or map projection.

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3. AIRCRAFT PLATFORM & NAVIGATION SYSTEM(S)

3.1 Brief Overview of Piper Chieftain

In 1983, NERC purchased a second-hand Piper Navajo Chieftain, type PA31-350, twin piston-engined aircraft that was subsequently modified by construction of two floor apertures and a forward navigation sight to enable operation of remote sensing equipment and aerial survey cameras. The NERC Piper Chieftain aircraft, designation G-NERC (Figure 3.1a), is fully airways equipped to allow flight in controlled airspace under Instrument Flight rules and in addition, is fitted with a Racal RNAV-2 navigation management system with Decca Mk.32. This equipment fit enables the aircraft to operate for surveys over both land and sea during the day or night. Table 3.1 provides the general specification for the NERC aircraft, including standard air speeds and endurance and the more restricted operational altitudes dictated by the sensor scanning and data recording characteristics.

Table 3.1. Specification of NERC survey aircraft (G-NERC)

Item	Specification
Type:	Piper PA31 350 Chieftain
Seating Capacity:	9
Seating Capacity on task:	5 maximum
Normal Seating Capacity on task:	4
Oxygen:	to all seat positions
Intercom:	to 5 seat positions
Cabin size:	Width 4ft-2in Height 4ft-3in Length 12ft-6in
Useful Load:	2050 lbs
Aircraft Power:	28 volts x 60 amps
True airspeed (transit):	150-170 knots
True Airspeed (on task):	100-170 knots
Maximum Authorised Altitude:	24,000 feet (8,000 metres)
Maximum Operational Altitude:	10,000 feet (3,000 metres)
Minimum Operational Altitude:	2,400 feet (800 metres)
Endurance (Range):	4 hours (950 n miles) approx, plus reserves †

† Endurance (range) varies greatly depending on True Airspeed and Altitude required for specific task.

Figure 3.1 (a) The NERC Piper Chieftain aircraft designation G-NERC.

Figure 3.1 (b) Interior of cabin showing Daedalus 1268 scan-head in middle foreground with IDS/ATM cabinet beyond including ATM display monitor (on left), *casi* display monitor (on right) and GPS display (above, on right).

3.2 Aircraft Sensor Layout

The general layout of the sensors is seen in the cross-sectional schematic in Figure 3.2, with the Daedalus 1268 scan head occupying the forward camera port and the RC-10 in the rear camera port. The *casi* instrument, being much smaller does not require a full-size camera aperture and has been located towards the rear of the plane in a custom built mounting. The sensor operator sits to the side of the ATM scan head facing the control console for the Integrated Data System (IDS) (Figure 3.1b). The cabinet, which runs the full width of the aircraft cabin, houses the IDS/ATM data acquisition and control system and includes the Barco display monitor for the ATM data (left). Although the data acquisition and recording system for the *casi* is housed in the rear of the cabin, the operator has access to the *casi* control keyboard and *casi* display monitor (right) for complete control of operations from this position. The *casi* Incident Light Sensor (ILS) which captures the downwelling solar irradiance through a cosine corrected collector is mounted on the roof above the pilot/co-pilots position. A fibre-optic cable runs the length of the aircraft to direct the light into the *casi* spectrometer head.

The RC-10 is mounted in the rear camera port and can be automatically controlled through use of a laptop control box and a Zeiss navigation sight, mounted in the co-pilot's (navigator's) position.

3.3 Navigation Aids & Ashtech GPS System Configuration

In addition to the standard radio navigation aids and two separate compass systems, the NERC aircraft was fitted, in 1993, with a state-of-the-art Ashtech 3DF Global Positioning Satellite (GPS) system. This provides improved in flight navigation and enables the acquisition of attitude and position information for geometric rectification of the sensor data. The Ashtech system consists of four separate antennae which are located on the aircraft cabin roof in a cruciform arrangement. Fore- and aft- antennae run along the centre line of the aircraft while the port and starboard antennae are located on short stubby winglets (Figure 3.1a) providing a separation of about 1.2metres. Inside the cabin are the four 6 channel receivers and the display panel which is located above the *casi* monitor (Figure 3.1b) and can be programmed to display a variety of navigational information for use by the sensor operator or the pilot/navigator. In non-differential mode the system can provide position in BNG coordinates or Latitude/Longitude to about 100metres accuracy. The theory and use of the Ashtech GPS system will be described in further detail in Chapter 10 on the geometric rectification.

Figure 3.2 Cross-sectional schematic of the NERC aircraft showing the general layout of equipment.

4. INTEGRATED DATA SYSTEM / ATM SENSOR

4.1 Overview of IDS Configuration

The Daedalus 1268 (Airborne Thematic Mapper- ATM) 11-channel multi-spectral scanner, hired for previous campaigns, was purchased by NERC, in 1993, to retain this airborne system in the UK. Ownership of the scanner enabled NERC to consider the upgrading of the data recording system from the heavy (~70Kg) High Density Digital Tape (HDDT) drive to fit in with a developing ground-data processing strategy which would remove the need for HDDT (1") to CCT (0.5") tape transcription and its associated specialised hardware. Following a tender exercise this upgrade design was substantially enhanced to completely replace the data acquisition electronics with data recording on removal 4Gb Hard-Disk (HD) winchesters, increasing capacity and flexibility, and with provision of a display monitor for the sensor operator to observe the quality and coverage of ATM data as it is collected.

Another main requirement of the upgrade was to enable the full potential of the Ashtech 3DF attitude and position reference system to be utilised by enabling synchronization of GPS information with scan line acquisition time from both the Daedalus 1268 scan-head and the *casí* system. Figure 4.1 is a schematic of the on-board Integrated Data System (IDS) illustrating the relationship between sensors and data flow. The 11 spectral channels of the Daedalus 1268 are digitised, along with the output of the roll gyro (12th channel), by the Azimuth Systems (AZ-16) hardware, and together with an accurate measure of scan-line acquisition time, are recorded on one of two 4Gb removal HDs. These are removable to enable easy transfer of data to DDS-2 DAT tapes at base, prior to data transcription by the ground processing system. In the rare event of both the on-board HDs becoming full during a single mission, or the operation of the aircraft away from base for an extended period, the data can be archived to a DAT drive within the on-board system to free up the HDs for further data acquisition. Time labelled information on GPS satellite ephemeris at 2Hz (0.5 second intervals) is also recorded in the data stream for later navigation processing and merging with ground-station GPS for differential correction of absolute position. Although the *casí* is operated independently of the IDS the asynchronous image frame acquisition timing of the *casí* is recorded via a coaxial cable port on the *casí* providing a timing pulse and an RS-232 serial line providing a scan count parameter.

4.2 ATM Specification & Data Acquisition Modes

At present, the Daedalus 1268 scan head optics and detector layout remain unchanged (Figure 4.2) and provide the standard 11 spectral channels (Table 4.1). These cover the visible and near-infrared (Ch 1-8), shortwave infrared (SWIR) (ch 9 & 10) and thermal infrared (TIR) (ch

Figure 4.1 Schematic diagram of the on-board Integrated Data System (IDS).

Daedalus Enterprises Inc.

Figure 4.2 Layout of optics and detectors in the Daedalus AADS1268 multispectral scanner

11) and include channels that closely match the seven spectral channels of the Landsat Thematic Mapper. Light, captured by the rotating scan mirror is split by dichroic filters into a number of light paths which are imaged onto detectors. Visible and near-infrared light is split by a prism before being imaged onto an array of silicon detectors (Chs 1-8). Middle-(shortwave), and thermal- infrared light is split, imaged and recorded on single detector elements held within three individual, liquid nitrogen (LN2) cooled, dewars (Chs 9, 10 and 11).

Table 4.1. Specification of the NERC IDS/ATM scanner.

Band	Band Edges		Landsat TM		ATM Specifications		AZ-16
	(μm)		bands	Original			
1	0.42	- 0.45				IFOV 2.5mrad	
2	0.45	- 0.52	1		716	Pixel swath	992/1984
3	0.52	- 0.60	2		85.92°	Digitized FOV	90°
4	0.605	- 0.625			72.86°	S-Bend correction	N/A
5	0.63	- 0.69	3				
6	0.695	- 0.75				Scan rate 12.5, 25, 50 scans/sec	
7	0.76	- 0.90	4		+ - 15°	Roll correction	N/A
8	0.91	- 1.05			8-bit (0-255)	Resolution	16-bit (0-65535)
9	1.55	- 1.75	5				
10	2.08	- 2.35	7				
11	8.5	- 13.0	6§		Two black-bodies for calibration of thermal channel		

§ Thermal band broadened for aircraft operation.

Table 4.1 also includes a number of changes that will occur with the replacement of the original Daedalus ABDE260 Video Digitizer by the AZ-16 hardware. These include the change from 716 pixels per scanline to 992 or 1984 samples per scanline, depending on scan speed, and total scan-angle or Field-Of-View (FOV) from 73° to 90°. At a scan-rate of 50 Hz (scans/sec) there will be 992 samples digitised by the electronics, while at 25 and 12.5 Hz there will be 992 or twice that (1984) samples recorded. This oversampling in the across-track dimension enables a better reconstruction of the scene variations and provides the basis for a more accurate geometric correction of the data, taking into account both the scanning characteristics of the ATM and the instantaneous vertical to the ground from the aircraft attitude. The 'disadvantage' is that the ATM Level 1b data products will be less visually correct than previously, since they will retain the panoramic distortion, inherent in mirror scan systems and the aircraft roll distortion removed from the original Daedalus 1268 by the 'S-bend' correction and the +15° roll compensation, respectively. The three axis-geometric correction (see Chapters 8 and 10) will however, provide a far superior geometric rectification of the data for both visual interpretation and quantitative work. The scan mirror has three synchronized speeds (12.5, 25, and 50 Hz), as with the original system, to optimize the scan-rate to more closely match data acquisition and coverage over the ground at various altitudes, thus avoiding any under-sampling or too much over-sampling of the data in the along-track (flightline) direction.

An approximately 10% overlap of successive scans is normally used to avoid missing areas on the ground caused by changes in aircraft velocity or attitude. Actual pixel size (ground spatial resolution) will be dependent on the flying altitude of the aircraft since the ATM sensor has a fixed Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) of 2.5mrad (~0.14°).

The IDS/ATM system also has an increased sensitivity with the upgrade from 8-bit to 16-bit resolution (256DN to 65536DN levels). This latter enhancement, in the number of digitized 'bits' of the A/D convertor, eliminates the need for the operator to set up 'gain-settings' for each channel to maximize recorded sensitivity in any one channel for a particular target. Unlike the first 10 channels, which are calibrated using a pre-, or post-mission laboratory test bench procedure, the thermal channel is calibrated by comparison in 'real-time' to two on-board black-bodies which can be set to just above and just below the maximum and minimum temperatures expected in the scene (-15°C to +50°C). These are imaged by the sensor during every scan, immediately before and after the scene pixels. The two blackbody temperatures and the sensor responses are recorded in the data stream for later radiometric calibration processing. Due to the increased quantization available for the IDS/ATM system the need for recording of the thermal channel at half the normal gain, as recorded into channel 12 of the Daedalus output, has been eliminated. This spare 12th channel will be used to record the Daedalus 1268 roll gyro which previously was used to provide an approximate 'real-time' roll correction and will now be used to monitor the aircraft roll at ATM scan-rates as a check on the slower, but more accurate, GPS-based attitude information.

4.3 Interim Solution

During the development phase of the new IDS/ATM scanner and before final commissioning of the system, prior to the 1996/97 airborne campaign, an 'Interim Solution' has been employed. This system uses the original Daedalus 1268 (ATM) data acquisition and recording system, as previously, but allows the collection of the necessary GPS-based attitude and position information and time synchronization for both the ATM and *casi* sensors. Data from the ATM has to be transcribed to CCTs and then copied to DAT tapes for ingestion into the ground-based data processing system. Data prior to July 1994 will not have had the Interim Solution navigation information recorded and, although it will be processed to produce standard data products (Chapter 8), will not be able to be parametrically geometrically corrected by the processing system. After July 1994, Interim Solution navigation information has been collected and both ATM and *casi* data will be able to be geometrically rectified to a map coordinate system using aircraft ephemeris. However, since the ATM is still using the original data acquisition system it will retain the original sensor radiometric and geometric characteristics. Interim Solution ATM data will have 716 pixel per scan line, roll and 'S-Bend' correction incorporated during data acquisition, and only 8-bit quantization (256 DN levels). Since all the ATM data, collected during 1994 and 1995, will be processed through the ground-based data processing system, it will automatically have the radiometric calibration coefficients applied for

the appropriate channel and channel gain-settings as recorded in the header information and will be output as scaled 16-bit integer data products

4.3.1 Data Characteristics

ATM data recorded under the Interim Solution will look exactly as previous Daedalus 1268 11ch ATM data, when displayed on an image processing system or produced on a hardcopy device. Figure 4.3 illustrates an example ATM flightline taken over the Llyn Brianne reservoir in mid-Wales on 28th November, 1994, Figure 4.3 (a) is a single channel greyscale image of the thermal band (ch 11) highlighting variations in surface radiant temperature. Figure 4.3 (b) is a three-band false-colour composite of channels 7, 9, and 5 (near-infrared, middle infrared and red) that is equivalent to a 4, 5, 3 band combination of the Thematic Mapper sensor on-board the Landsat satellite. It clearly differentiates between the bright multi-coloured grass covered moorland and the forested areas. Sinuous tracks within the conifer forest plantations are lined with deciduous trees (pale green) and therefore show up in sharp contrast to the evergreens (brown) in this autumn image. The reservoir surface can also be clearly discriminated by its much higher radiant temperature in (a) and by the near zero values of reflectance (up-welling radiance) of water in the red and infrared image combination in (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.3 Imagery of the Llyn Brianne reservoir in Mid-Wales, taken with the NERC Daedalus 1268 Airborne Thematic Mapper on November 28th, 1994. (a) is a greyscale image, recorded in the thermal infrared (ch 11). (b) is a simultaneously recorded, false-colour composite of the same scene, formed from near-infrared, middle infrared and red channels (ch. 7,9, 5) to R,G,B.

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5. CASI SENSOR

5.1 Overview of Configuration & Specification

The Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (*CASI*), produced by Itres Research of Canada, is a two-dimensional CCD array based pushbroom imaging spectrograph (Table 5.1).

Table 5.1 Specification of the NERC *casi* sensor.

Parameter	Description
Field of View	42° across-track (custom foreoptics lens)
Aperture	f/2.8 - f/11 (Automated iris control)
Spectral range	400 - 915nm
Spatial samples	512 spatial pixels
Spectral samples	288 at 1.8nm intervals (3nm FWHM @ 650nm)
Dynamic range	12-bits (4096 levels)
Recording	EXAbyte 8500 (8mm digital helical scan tape recorder)
Operating Modes	
• Spatial Mode	512 pixels across swath, up to 18 spectral bands (fully programmable).
• Spectral Mode	full spectrum (288 channels) for up to 39 look directions spread across swath (4, 8, 12, or 16 pixel spacing between look directions). Includes a monochromatic image at full spatial resolution (Scene Recovery Channel).
• Enhanced Spectral Mode	full spectrum (288 channels) in a block of 101 adjacent spatial pixels.
• Full Frame	512 pixels across swath x 288 spectral pixels (~1-2 sec. integration time limits use to laboratory calibration or ground-based field use).
Downwelling incident light sensor (ILS)	
Lumogen coating for enhancement of blue response below 450nm	

One dimension of the 578x288 element array is used to obtain an image frame of 512 spatial pixels of the surface that builds up a flightline of data as the aircraft moves forward (Figure 5.1). On the front of the *casi* camera head is a custom foreoptic lens with 42° FOV which has been designed to provide optimum focussing across the *casi* wavelength range (achromatic focus). Light levels entering the spectrometer through the lens can be varied by the operator via an automated iris control (Settings 1 to 5) which are approximately equivalent to apertures of f11, f8, f5.6, f4, and f2.8. Setting 0 causes the iris to close completely for use in collecting in-flight dark-current readings, prior to and after a flightline. After passing through a 15µm wide spectrographic slit, a reflection grating disperses the light from each pixel over the 400 to 915nm spectral range and is recorded by the 288 detectors on the orthogonal dimension of the CCD. The row spacing

Figure 5.1 Imaging concept of the *casi* CCD pushbroom spectrograph.

on the CCD equates to a spectral sampling of 1.8nm. However, the effective bandwidth of a single row has a value of 2.9nm FWHM at 650nm, resulting from the optical system and convolution of the slit width and detector size. A section of the array, masked off from imaging scene pixels, is used to record electronic noise, frame shift smear and scattered light contributions for use in post processing calibration. Additionally, a portion of this hidden section is used to image light, transmitted via a fibre optic bundle, from a downwelling Incident Light Sensor (ILS) mounted in the roof of the aircraft. Light from the ILS is dispersed, imaged onto the CCD, and recorded in spectral bands identical to those from the scene viewed by the *casi*. The analogue signals from the complete CCD array are digitized by a 12-bit A/D convertor providing 4096 digital levels and recorded on a high density EXAbyte 8500 tape. Signal levels can be adjusted via control of both the auto-iris aperture and the integration time of the CCD, maximizing use of the full 12-bit range without saturating the detectors. The sensor operator controls the *casi* system via a keyboard and a monitor that displays the instrument settings, signal levels, and a scrolling real-time window of the data as it is collected.

5.2 Data Acquisition Modes

Although it is possible to image all 512 spatial pixels and all 288 spectral channels simultaneously (Full Frame Mode), in practice a compromise is required to avoid excessive smearing of along track pixels caused by the length of time taken to perform the read out for all elements of the array. The compromise takes the form of using two main operating modes - spatial and spectral modes which reduce the data recording requirements.

5.2.1 Spatial Mode & Default Bandsets

Spatial mode records data from all 512 spatial dimension pixels, but from a limited number of programmable bands (max. 18) by selection and summation of the 1.8nm resolution detector elements (Figure 5.2a). This provides an equivalent, spatially contiguous, multi-band data set to that recorded by the ATM sensor. A spatial bandset can be formed from single detector elements or unique summations of two or more adjacent detector elements located throughout the entire spectral range of the *casi* (400-915nm). A single detector element cannot be summed into more than one spatial band, even if the spatial bands are adjacent. The number, locations and bandwidths of the different bands can be set up, according to the user application, to cover either broad spectrally different regions eg. blue, green, red, and near-infrared, or at precisely placed narrow wavelengths to measure specific phenomena eg. chlorophyll fluorescence, red-edge position, or atmospheric absorptions. Users can provide their own spatial bandsets for programming and use by the sensor operator or can select one of the default bandsets set-up for standard applications. Default bandsets for terrestrial vegetation and ocean colour applications are included in Appendix B with a general description of the purpose of each band.

Figure 5.2 (a) CASI Spatial Mode configuration.

Figure 5.2 (b) CASI Spectral Mode configuration.

5.2.2 Spectral Mode & Scene Recovery Channel

In spectral mode the full spectral profile of 288 channels can be recorded, but from a limited number of look directions, or pixel positions, spread as a rake across the ground (max. 39) (Figure 5.2b). The 39 'tines' of this 'push-rake spectrometer' mode can be located with either 4, 8, 12 or 16 non-imaged pixels (look spacing) between each recorded spatial pixel, according to the user requirement; concentrating pixels together for high spatial resolution or spreading them out across the entire swath for good spatial coverage. Due to the missing spatial pixels it may sometimes be difficult to precisely locate the rake of spectral pixels within a scene. To offset this problem the Spectral Mode simultaneously produces a single full spatial band, formed from a single detector element, which is inherently co-registered with the separate look-directions. Using this Scene Recovery Channel (SRC) it is possible to locate the pixels positions of the spectral data within the scene. When selecting Spectral Mode for an airborne remote sensing mission the operator needs to program the *casi* with the spread of the push-rake, either 4, 8, 12 or 16 non-imaged pixels between the 'tines', and the channel wavelength (nm) for the SRC.

5.2.3 Enhanced Spectral Mode

Recently, through hardware speed increases and software development, the *casi* has gained a new mode - Enhanced Spectral Mode, where the full 3D data cube can be alternatively sliced into a single block of 101 adjacent spatial pixels imaged for all 288 spectral channels. This mode can be further extended into a series with increasing spatial coverage (more spatial pixels) at the expense of decreasing spectral resolution (fewer, wider channels). Each output band being formed by either a single detector element (101 x 288) or summations of adjacent detectors ie. summations of CCD row 1+2, etc. or 1+2+3, etc. thus maintaining a consistent integration time. Table 5.2 shows some typical examples of the look directions versus number of spectral channels, indicating the effect on frame rate and pixel resolution.

Table 5.2. Typical configurations in Enhanced Spectral Mode.

Look Directions	# Spectral Channels	Spectral Resolution (nm)	Approximate Frame Rate (frames/sec)	Spatial Resolution W x L (m)	Altitude (m a.g.l)
101	288	1.8	7	3.7 x 7.3	3049
101	48	10.8	38	1.2 x 1.2	1000
203	144	3.6	7	3.7 x 7.3	3049
303	96	5.6	7	3.7 x 7.3	3049
511	48	10.8	9	3.7 x 7.3	3049

* Note: Aircraft speed over ground is assumed to be 100knots (51 m/s) for above calculations.(m.a.g.l.) - metres above ground level.

However, both the Spectral and Enhanced Spectral Modes have a distinct drawback, since integration times are much longer than for Spatial Mode. This precludes the general use of these high data rate modes at low altitudes where fast integration times are required to maintain the squareness of pixels (pixel widths being smaller because of the low altitude). If this is not attainable at the altitude required, an aspect ratio (pixel length to width) of 2:1 or more may have to be selected by the operator.

5.2.4 Full Frame Mode

Full Frame Mode is generally only used during laboratory calibrations since the integration times (1-2 seconds) are too long to be used during airborne flights without tremendous smearing of the image. However, it may be possible to use this mode when the *casi* is mounted on a ground-based motion tripod to view static objects for use in, for example, colour perception studies.

5.3 Data Characteristics

5.3.1 Spatial Mode Data

Figure 5.4 is a three band colour composite of *casi* spatial mode data of Thorney Island, W. Sussex and the surrounding waters, using the default SeaWiFS / ocean colour bandset (Ch 7,5,3 to R,G,B) . This image was taken from an altitude of about 10,000ft (3,300m), on the 25th July, 1994 and provides a 512 pixel swath of approximately 4.5m x 4.5m spatial resolution. The geometric distortion of the 'straight' runways is due to the roll of the NERC aircraft along the flightline which will be corrected in higher level products

5.3.2 Spectral Mode Data and Scene Recovery Channel

The same flightline over Thorney Island was repeated in spectral mode to produce the images in Figure 5.5. Figure 5.5 (a) shows a three band colour composite using equivalent channels to the centre wavelengths of the spatial bandset in Figure 5.4. The image is composed of 39 look-directions, but with each pixel having the full 288 spectral channels. The pixels were collected with a pixel spacing of 4, such that each imaged look direction is separated by 4 pixels that are not imaged. The 39 look directions therefore fill the central third of the swath of the spatial image. Figure 5.5 (b) shows the single channel Scene Recovery Channel (SRC) acquired simultaneously with the full spectral data and illustrates the true look direction spacing. It should be noted that the spectral data in this image looks very much compressed in comparison to the full spatial image. This is due to the much longer integration times required for spectral mode data and the resultant longer pixels, covering the same ground distance with fewer lines.

Figure 5.4 CASI Spatial Mode Imagery.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.4 CASI Spectral Mode imagery. (a) as stored in data file, (b) as recorded in original push-rake separation, superimposed on monochrome Scene Recovery Channel.

6. RC-10 CAMERA

6.1 Overview of Configuration & Specification

6.2 Film Types, Resolution & Basic/Stereo

To be published shortly

7. MISSION / FLIGHT PLANNING

There are many trade-offs to be made between conflicting sensor parameters in optimizing data acquisition from the ATM and *casi* sensors, such as ground spatial resolution, channel selection and in maximizing signal-to-noise. Other mission parameters involve decisions on the length, direction and overlap of multiple flightlines, timing of flights during the day or season, flight restrictions (Air Traffic Control), and acceptable weather conditions. Many of these factors are additionally influenced by the performance of the current aircraft in terms of speed, endurance and maximum altitude. The sections in this chapter discuss these parameters and may help the user in defining the requirements of an airborne remote sensing campaign and how to complete the ARS proposal form for future use of the facility.

7.1 Ground Spatial Resolution

7.1.1 IDS/ATM

The ground spatial resolution (pixel size) of the ATM is defined both by the optical characteristics of the scan head, which provides an Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) of 2.5mrad (~0.14°), and the aircraft altitude. Pixel length and pixel width are both defined by this 2.5mrad IFOV, but ground dimensions will vary differently as a function of the scan-angle away from nadir. Figure 7.1 is a schematic diagram of the scan geometry of a single off-nadir pixel of the Daedalus 1268. Given the total Field-of-View (FOV) of the new IDS/ATM system (90°) and the number of samples per scan line, the off-nadir scan angle (Θ) for a given pixel can be calculated. Using 2.5mrad for both β and χ , the ground pixel dimensions in the X (along-scan) and Y (along-track) directions can be calculated for any given off-nadir angle Θ , using the following equations:

$$e_x = \beta Z \sec^2\Theta \quad \text{and} \quad e_y = \chi Z \sec\Theta$$

where e_x is the pixel width and e_y the pixel length, β and χ are the IFOV in each direction (=2.5mrad), Z is the altitude (metres), and Θ is the off-nadir scan angle.

Figure 7.2 illustrates the change in pixel dimensions and swath width with altitude for the new IDS/ATM system. It also shows the change in pixel dimensions at the maximum off-nadir scan angle where the square nadir pixels have become enlarged rectangles. The main difference with the introduction of the IDS/ATM is that pixel sampling interval in the along-scan direction is completely different from the original Daedalus 1268. The original Daedalus 1268 used an electronic sampling system which allowed non-equal timing intervals during the mirror scan cycle to produce pixels on the ground at equal ground spacings in the X direction. This 'S-

X direction - along-scan
 Y direction - along-track
 Z direction - altitude (height above horizontal surface)

Θ = scan angle from nadir
 Z = height
 β = angular resolution (along-scan)
 χ = angular resolution (along-track)
 e_Y = ground resolution element dimension in along-scan direction
 e_X = ground resolution element dimension in along-track direction

Figure 7.1 Schematic diagram of the scan geometry of a single off-nadir pixel.

**Swath Width and Spatial Resolution
for IDS/ATM sensor (+-45 deg FOV)**

Figure 7.2 ATM pixel dimensions and swath width against altitude.

bend' correction is so called because straight scene features, such as roads or railway lines, running diagonally across the image would otherwise be represented in the output image by 'S' shaped curves due to the unequal sample spacing. The IDS/ATM system uses an equal timing/angular sampling interval across the whole scanline which includes the inherent 'S-bend' distortion. This is more than compensated by the large oversampling that can be attained as a result of the very fast A/D conversion. Although the ground instantaneous pixel dimensions can be calculated as above, the sampling interval is controlled by

$$X_i = Z \tan \Theta_i$$

where X_i is the distance from nadir in metres of the i th pixel (from nadir), Z is altitude in metres, and Θ_i is the scan angle of the i th pixel.

The angular sampling interval will be $90^\circ / 992$ samples at 50Hz scan-rate = $\sim 0.091^\circ$ per pixel or $90^\circ / 1984$ samples at 12.5 and 25Hz = $\sim 0.045^\circ$ per pixel. Exact sample spacing on the ground will also be dependent on the attitude of the aircraft and altitude, so can only be calculated in combination with output from the navigation information which will be supplied with the data. A full geometric model will be supplied to enable users to calculate the viewing geometry of each pixel on a pixel by pixel and line by line basis.

The scan geometry is further complicated by the forward motion of the aircraft during the scan mirror rotation since adjacent pixel centres will advance as the aircraft moves forward during a scanline. However, the short time required for the signal integration of an individual pixel means that there is negligible smearing of the pixel and the pixel length is dominated by the IFOV. As can be seen there is clear relationship between the pixel length (in metres), determined by the aircraft altitude, and the distance over the ground (in metres) that the aircraft moves between successive scan lines. As an example, if the aircraft flies at a nominal speed of 120kts (~ 62 metres/sec) it will move forward approximately 1.24, 2.48, 4.96 metres during one scanline at the three different scan-speeds of 50, 25, and 12.5 scans/second. If the aircraft is flying at an altitude of 1,000 metres the nadir pixel length will be approximately 2.5metres. Selecting a scan-rate of 50 Hz at this altitude would dramatically oversample the ground, while at 12.5 Hz it would undersample the image. The sensor operator will select the most appropriate scan-rate to avoid any undersampling, but varying degrees of oversampling are unavoidable. The exact scan geometry used during data acquisition of a particular flightline will be determined by the geometric sensor model and aircraft attitude, altitude and velocity and be used in the geometric rectification process.

7.1.2 CASI

The *casi* sensor produces a ground spatial resolution where pixel width and length are essentially independent of each other. The along-track spatial resolution or pixel length is a function of the integration time and the speed of the instrument over the ground. The required integration time is itself determined by the signal level and the number of channels requested by the user. For a given light level input to the instrument, the number of channels requested by the user determines the minimum integration time and, for an average aircraft speed over the ground, the equivalent pixel length in metres. Along-track resolution can be calculated with the following formula:

$$PL = (IT * GS) / 1000$$

where, PL = pixel length in metres
IT = integration time in milliseconds
GS = ground speed in metres/second

As an example, a 14 band configuration with a 51ms integration time, collected in an aircraft flying at 120 knots would have a pixel length of:

Conversion of knots to metres/second

$$(120 * 1.852) / 3.6 = 61.73 \text{ m/s}$$
$$PL = (51\text{ms} * 61.73\text{m/s}) / 1000 = 3.15 \text{ metres}$$

Figure 7.3 shows the pixel length and minimum integration time for various numbers of bands for an average speed (120 knots) of the NERC aircraft. It should also be noted that since one band is reserved for measurement of Frame Shift Smear (FSS) which is used during radiometric correction, the present *casi* system has a possible maximum of 18 spatial bands. In practice, this number of spatial channels may be unattainable, due to aircraft altitude and spatial resolution restrictions, as will be explained in the following sections.

The across-track spatial resolution or pixel width is a function of the CCD detector element size, focal length of the imaging lens, which for a given *casi* are both constant, and the altitude of the aircraft. Clearly, as the aircraft altitude increases so does the pixel width and consequently also the total swath width which is, for spatial mode and the SRC, simply 512 times the pixel width. The NERC *casi* has a total field of view of 42° produced by a 10mm focal length lens and a CCD detector size of 15µm. The across-track resolution, which is the same for all pixels in a band of Spatial Mode data and the Spectral Mode Scene Recovery Channel and each of the Spectral Mode look directions, can be calculated using the following formula:

Pixel Length and Integration Time
for NERC CASI (aircraft at 120kts)

Figure 7.3.CASI pixel length vs integration time.

$$PW = (\text{CCD Detector Width} / \text{Focal Length}) * \text{Altitude}$$

where,
CCD Detector Width = 0.015mm
Focal Length = 10.0mm
Altitude = metres above ground

As an example, if the NERC aircraft flew at 3000 metres (~10,000ft) above ground level the across-track pixel resolution would be:

$$PW = (0.015 / 10.0) * 3000 = 4.5 \text{ metres}$$

Due to the optical characteristics of this 'push-broom' sensor, which samples every scene pixel along a scanline in the same ratio as the fixed, and equal inter-detector dimension (15 μ m), all pixels in a scanline are of equal width. The swath width of a spatial mode band or scene recovery channel will therefore become, for this example, 4.5 metres * 512 pixels = 2304 metres. Figure 7.4 shows the pixel width and total swath width against altitude of the aircraft.

Depending on the priority the user places on either a specific ground resolution (altitude) or specific number of bands, the figures and formulae above can be used to explore the trade-off in flight/sensor parameters for a particular mission. Choosing a specific ground spatial resolution and a requirement for near square pixels will determine the maximum number of bands allowable in spatial mode. Conversely choosing a specific number of bands in a *cas*i bandset will determine the pixel length and, in retaining near-square pixels, determine pixel width and hence the altitude the aircraft must be flown at. For Spectral Mode and Enhanced Spectral Mode, where minimum integration times are much longer it is sometimes impossible to attain square pixels and aspect ratios of 2:1 or more may result.

7.2 Channel / Mode Selection & Maximizing Sensor Signal

7.2.1 IDS/ATM

There is no channel selection required by the user for the ATM sensor since all 11 channels can be recorded at all times. The main sensor option with the ATM concerns the setting up, by the operator, of the two on-board black-body temperatures for the thermal channel (8-14 μ m). The operator generally sets these to just below and just above the maximum scene temperatures that are being recorded by the sensor during transit flights to the target area and over similar terrain. Closely bracketing the likely scene temperatures provides two ideally placed points for the DN to radiance calibration. However, unlike the original Daedalus 1268, the change in blackbody temperatures is not required to increase instrument sensitivity since this has been enormously increased by the change from 8-bit to 16-bit A/D conversion.

For night-time data acquisition by the ATM for studies solely with the thermal channel, the

**Swath Width and Spatial Resolution
for NERC CASI (42 deg FOV)**

Figure 7.4. CASI pixel width and swath width against altitude.

solar reflective channels (1-10) can be discarded to save on further processing and storage space, since there will be no usable signal recorded.

7.2.2 CASI

Sensor mode selection becomes more important with the *casi* due to its programmable nature and inherent flexibility of data acquisition. Generally, *casi* data acquisition is carried out using Spatial Mode with between 8 and 14 channels specifically selected for the particular user application (see Appendix B for default bandsets). Spectral Mode and to some extent Enhanced Spectral Mode, with their limited spatial coverage, are used for reconnaissance flightlines where no *a priori* knowledge of the spectral features of the target are known. Imagery from these modes can be used to define the spectral positions of diagnostic features and used to derive a new spatial mode bandset. This can then be flown with full spatial coverage on later missions. Some missions may use a combination of spatial and spectral mode flightlines in this way.

Channel selection for spatial mode bandsets should aim to distinguish between diagnostic spectral features at the same time as maximizing the recorded signal. The recorded signal is a function of both the received light energy, which is a function of solar irradiance and surface reflectance, and the system characteristics. The latter is determined by the lens aperture, CCD integration time, and the sensitivity of the silicon CCD detector. A *casi* spatial bandset is normally generated with bands approximately 10nm wide, by summation of the signal from about 5 or 6 detector elements. The bandsets are generated by the operator, as files on the *casi*, prior to a mission and can be set-up for use within a few seconds by loading the appropriate configuration file. The user needs to specify a default bandset or specify the bands individually by quoting a centre wavelength and bandwidth (in nanometres) for each band. The operator will implement these requirements by setting up which detector elements are to be summed into each band from the nearest available centre wavelengths of the current spectral calibration table (see Appendix B). Spectral calibration is carried out at regular intervals to maintain an accurate detector/wavelength relationship, since this may change during upgrades to the *casi* instrument or slowly drift over long time periods. The alignment of the detector array and use of a reflection grating produces a linear increase in spectral sampling interval with increasing wavelength, rising from 1.76nm at 401.05nm (detector element 287) to 1.83nm at 915.02nm (detector element 0). The spectral Full-Width Half Maximum (FWHM) bandwidth, which is a complex function of the light dispersion in the instrument, varies with wavelength as seen in Figure 7.5. Figure 7.6 provides a schematic spectral response for an example spatial band, illustrating the difference between spectral sampling interval (1.76nm@442nm) and spectral bandwidth or dispersion (4.08nm at 459nm) and showing the resultant shape of the normalised response curve. Due to the sampling interval the exact location of upper and lower band edges are to the nearest half detector width. Ideally detectors should be included within a band to provide a normalised response FWHM bandwidth closest to the desired lower and upper band edges requested by the user. The leading slope on the top of the spectral response curve is due

Figure 7.5 CASI spatial bandwidth vs wavelength (nm).

Figure 7.6 Schematic of CASI spatial bandset.

to the variation in spectral sampling and bandwidth across the individual detector elements being summed. Other band summations may show trailing slopes or crenulated tops to the response curve, as seen in the spectral responses of the default bandsets (Appendix B).

Individual bands may vary in width where narrower spectral features are to be detected or distinguished from adjacent noise signals such as for chlorophyll fluorescence studies or in avoiding (or selecting) atmospheric absorptions. Since the sensitivity of the *casi* instrument is wavelength dependent, decreasing towards the extremes of the spectral range, more light is required near the ends of the wavelength range to give a similar signal. This extra light can be obtained by increasing the bandwidth of bands located near the ends of the *casi* spectral range while maintaining narrower bands towards the centre. For studies of ocean colour, where short wavelengths (<500nm) contain diagnostic information in broad regions, but at very low light levels, 15 to 20nm wide bands would increase the light gathered and increase the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). At the long wavelength range this could also be applied since the CCD sensitivity and the light reflectance from water beyond the red portion of the spectrum (670nm) are both dropping off rapidly. Conversely for images acquired over terrestrial targets with vegetation cover, wide bands in the near -infrared would soon saturate due to the very high surface reflectance at these wavelengths. In this case, the original band could be reduced in width or split into two or more bands covering the same wavelength range.

Users should be aware of the trade-offs, between CCD sensitivity and input light level for the target or targets to be imaged and, in general, try to achieve a uniform signal level for all bands. The operator can then adjust both the lens aperture and integration time to utilize the full quantization range of the A/D convertor in all bands simultaneously for a given absolute light level. It should be remembered that the best achromatic focus is achieved at an equivalent f-stop of f8 (iris aperture setting of 2) and that, consequently there will be some additional trade-off between lens aperture setting and integration time to achieve the required input light level. The signal strength can be varied in this way, by the operator, by reference to the display screen bar graph, which displays peak signal values for each band in spatial mode on a line by line basis. A minimum signal of 25% of full-scale is recommended for reasonable signal-to-noise ratios; a maximum of 90% of full scale, to avoid saturation from unexpectedly bright targets. It should be noted that data from saturated bands, within an otherwise valid pixel, cannot be recovered through later processing.

In *casi* Spectral Mode and Enhanced Spectral Mode the minimum integration time is generally longer than for spatial mode due to sensor readout constraints. For specific low altitude flights, elongated pixels may occur, as explained in section 7.1. Referring to Table 5.2, it can be seen that the number of summed channels and spatial pixels (look directions) in Enhanced Spectral Mode can be varied to reduce the integration time and hence pixel length. The Scene Recovery Channel (SRC) in Spectral Mode can be selected from the whole *casi* wavelength range, but it may be optimal to select a wavelength where signal levels are expected to be high since it is formed from only a single detector element. It can be requested for programming by the operator by specifying the centre wavelength (in nanometres) of the channel.

7.3 Flightline Parameters & Timing Criteria

As described, in the above sections, flightline swath width is a function of the altitude flown by the aircraft, increasing as the altitude increases. Flightline length, in terms of the number of scan lines, is also a function of altitude since at low altitude the pixel lengths of the ATM and *casi* are smaller and there are therefore, more lines needed to cover a given ground distance. The ATM is governed by the three scan speeds (12.5, 25 and 50 scanlines per second), the *casi* is governed by the integration time which determines the number of image frames recorded per second. Maximum flightline lengths are determined by the recording capacity for each sensor, ATM through the IDS system and the 4Gb disk drives, *casi*, via the capacity of an EXAbyte tape. Each 4Gb disk of the IDS has a capacity of about 160,000 scanlines which at the three different scan rates of 12.5, 25, and 50 scans/second allows a maximum recording time of approximately 213, 107, and 53 minutes. This is a far greater data recording capacity than would ever be used for a single continuous flightline. However, the 2 x 4Gb capacity represents the total capacity of the IDS/ATM system for all flightlines in a single mission, before data has to be backed up to the internal DAT drive and the hard-disk(s) cleared for re-use. The total mission capacity of the *casi* is only limited by the number of EXAbyte tapes (1.15Gb) that are carried in the aircraft on any one mission. Each tape allows about 38 minutes of continuous recording before the tape needs changing, taking about a minute to load and initialize for use. These data capacity limits have been designed to be more than adequate to cope for all the current and short-term future needs of the facility. However, developments are already in progress to provide a dual EXAbyte tape system for the *casi*, doubling capacity or allowing improvements in data acquisition.

Ideally, flightlines are drawn up by the user on appropriate map bases, at least 1:50,000 scale or better, and included with the completed airborne campaign application. The directions to be flown for single or multiple flightlines should be chosen with care. It would be normal for flightlines to run directly over and parallel with elongated ground targets, reducing the requirement to a single flightline (Figure 7.7a). However, it should be borne in mind that most airborne remotely sensed data, acquired in the optical domain suffer, to some degree, from atmospheric distortions. These can manifest themselves as a brightening towards the edges of the image (limb-brightening), due to increases in atmospheric scattering, caused by changes in the sun-target-sensor angle and to increases in path length. The asymmetry and amount of atmospheric distortion is a function of the azimuth of the flightline, in relation to the azimuth of the sun and its elevation. Flying perpendicular to the solar azimuth creates the maximum amount and maximum asymmetry of the distortion, while flying directly towards or away from the sun, reduces these effects to a minimum. If the reduction of atmospheric distortions is critical to the particular airborne mission / user application, the mission should be flown to cover the total area of the ground target with parallel flightlines flown in or out of the sun (Figure 7.7b). This can be important for terrestrial targets, but essential for aquatic targets to avoid the effects of the strong specular reflection or 'sun-glint' from the water surface.

Figure 7.7 Flightline direction(s) in relation to solar azimuth. a) parallel to target azimuth, b) parallel to solar azimuth.

Multiple parallel flightline should be flown with a 20-30% overlap to ensure complete coverage of the target and to avoid missing any section due to changes in aircraft attitude or drift as it flies over the ground. Generally, multiple overlapping flightlines should be flown in one direction only so that aircraft speed in relation to head wind or side drift (crab-angle) are kept similar for each flightline. Flying alternate directions can cause major changes in along-track pixel resolution between flightlines, due to the possible change in over the ground speed, flying with or against any head or tail winds.

Timing of the flightline(s) also need to be considered carefully. Following the above criteria of flying towards or away from the sun requires a knowledge of the solar azimuth which varies with time of day. For example, a morning flight might be in a NW-SE direction, near midday in a N-S direction and in the afternoon from NE-SW, all flown towards the sun. In practice the pilot/navigator may prefer to fly away from the sun's direction, having established its azimuth from the target, to avoid glare, improve visibility and flight safety, but this may be precluded by prevailing wind direction. The timing criteria also concerns the solar elevation. Early morning or late afternoon flights will encounter a low sun angle, causing long shadows and enhancement of topographic features at the expense of lower light levels. Some applications may require these conditions, but in general, most flights are carried out between +- 2hrs of solar noon, giving high sun angles, reducing shadow effects, minimising atmospheric scattering distortions and providing maximum light levels for data acquisition. Timing of flights may also be controlled by the nature of the target such as with inter-tidal zones, where low tide for a particular area will vary and tides tables reviewed in advance of a proposal submission.

A particular exception to these diurnal timing constraints applies to the use of thermal data from the ATM. Channel 11 of the ATM is responsive to thermal radiation emitted by the ground and can therefore be used, irrespective of solar illumination. Although the thermal data can be acquired during the day along with all the other wavelengths, some applications can benefit from thermal data collected pre- and post dawn to derive a measure of thermal inertia of the surface. A flight line is flown around 1hr before dawn, when surface temperatures are at a minimum and then again about an hour after sunrise. The sun heats up the surface, with some materials heating up faster due to differential heat capacity. Comparison of imagery from the two flightlines can be used to derive this heat capacity or thermal inertia which can be diagnostic of surface material composition or moisture content.

Seasonal variations of solar azimuth and elevation can constrain some missions due to the length of daylight hours over the year. Timing may also be critical for particular applications where multi-date flightlines are required to monitor changes in growth status of crops or in relation to spring or neap tides. If the application requires flights on days where Earth observation satellites are covering the same area, knowledge of their repeat cycles are important.

Base maps included with the application should contain, if possible, the likely flightline dimensions (swath width and length), derived from a knowledge of the user required altitude/spatial resolution (see section 7.1) and flight orientation or at least a clearly marked maximum area of interest and any critical zones that **MUST** be covered.

It should be borne in mind, particularly by new users, of the large data volumes that airborne remote sensing can generate. Table 7.1 gives the data size in Megabytes (Mb) of typical flightlines of ATM and *casi* data. Requests for very high spatial resolution data over large areas of terrain or high temporal resolution repeat missions will require a large number of flightlines which will take a substantial amount of time to acquire and process. Users, both new and experienced, are requested to apply for the minimum necessary to fully meet their science objectives as this not only assists the most efficient use of the facility, but also reduces wasted data analysis by the user. Excessive requests may be reduced by the ARSF Steering Committee during the review process and a revised set of flights offered to the user. New users, unfamiliar with the capabilities of the facility's sensors, or users developing a new application of the airborne remotely sensed data may be advised to reduce the overall spatial coverage of their proposal to acquire a reconnaissance data set on which to test the application. This may, however, result in an increased number of smaller flightlines, using various sensor modes or at additional spatial resolutions to provide a comprehensive dataset, on which to determine the optimum mission / sensor parameters for future applications for use of the facility.

Table 7.1 Data size for typical ATM and *casi* flightlines

Sensor / Mode	No. Scan lines	Data Size (Mb) [†]
IDS/ATM (11 Bands)	2,000	~44/87§
<i>CASI</i> Spatial Mode (14 Bands)	2,000	~29
Spectral Mode (39 Look Directions & SRC)	2,000	~45
Enhanced Spectral Mode (101x288)	2,000	~116

[†] Data size in Megabytes (Mb) for imagery only, ie. not including navigation or header information. § The IDS/ATM system can produce twice the number of samples per line at 12.5 and 25 Hz than at 50Hz. (NB: For the *casi* 2,000 scanlines represents a 3km flightline at 1.5m resolution / ~3,300ft altitude or a 9km flightline at 4.5m resolution / ~10,000ft altitude)

It is also worth considering the request for both ATM and *casi* sensors to be used with each flightline since the deployment to the test-site under similar optimum conditions is much more costly than the marginal extra cost of processing the 2nd sensor data. Following geometric rectification the two sensor data sets can be georeferenced to the same map projection and pixel size. This allows the synergistic analysis of information from different wavelength regions ie. high spectral resolution visible data from the *casi* and thermal data from the ATM, as would be highly beneficial for studies of biological productivity and current dynamics in oceans and

coastal waters. Many applications may benefit from this synergism, beyond the original requirements or expectations of the Principal Investigator. The ARSFSC may consider it useful to fly both sensors together, as a default, since archiving combined datasets covering the entire optical spectrum may prove invaluable for future data requests from the ARS data archive.

7.4 Restricted Airspace / Air Traffic Control / Flight Operations

In planning a mission to meet the users requirements, the navigator (ARS operations coordinator) must ensure that they meet with Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) and current Air Traffic Control (ATC) restrictions applying over the target area. The airways within and around the UK are the busiest in the world with civilian and military air traffic, both of which may have controlled air space/airways or restricted danger areas. There may be total exclusion zones near military bases and firing ranges or restricted flight levels above or below commercial air lanes. The navigator has to file a flight plan and get the necessary flight permissions in advance of each mission. NERC has a very good rapport with the National Air Traffic Service and can generally get entry into the airways with the minimum of fuss. Some areas may require contact with local ATCs on the day of, or even at the beginning of a flight run, and last minute withdrawal of permission may cause a flightline or mission to be aborted. Air safety will always be of paramount importance in any NERC airborne remote sensing activities. Flight restrictions apart, airborne campaigns are organised to maximise the collection of good airborne data for the user, based on the vast operational experience of the flight crew - pilot, navigator/ARS coordinator and sensor operator. The users should provide as much information as possible on the scientific requirements and restrictions of their proposal and leave the operational implementation to the flight crew to meet these in the most efficient and practicable way.

7.5 Weather Conditions

It is estimated that there are only about 40 totally clear sky days in the UK per year with the rest affected by some fraction of cumulus or high level cloud. The proportion of cloud acceptable during any particular mission is highly dependent on the user application with some experiments, for example, developing atmospheric corrections algorithms or calibrating airborne or satellite sensors, requiring near perfect conditions, while other surveys, not as dependent on the irradiance distribution, producing excellent results with 20-25% cloud cover in the area. The critical aspect in most missions is to ensure that, although there are clouds around, they do not directly obscure or indirectly shadow the target during data acquisition. Since homogeneity of the solar irradiance is often more important than absolute level, in deriving consistent surface reflectance, a small proportion of surveys could even be carried out under completely overcast (uniform) cloud cover. Even in what seems pretty clear skies (no cumulus) the presence of high level cirrus clouds can have an affect on the absolute level of

irradiance at the target and consequently the signal level at the aircraft. Horizontal visibility is only loosely connected with vertical visibility and some missions may be impossible due to extremely high haze conditions between the aircraft and the ground. It should be borne in mind that most of the atmospheric constituents impairing optical remote sensing are concentrated in the bottom few kilometers of the atmosphere and that at 10,000ft the aircraft is viewing through about 90% of the atmosphere's optical thickness.

Weather conditions can vary dramatically and rapidly, and timing of flights should be considered in the light of local or seasonal history on the build of late morning cumulus or dissipation of early morning mist/fog. The weather in the days preceding a mission may also be relevant in the requirement for a lengthy period of dry weather or conversely fresh precipitation prior to a flight when applications involve soil or vegetation moisture, or low/high sediment runoff into streams and estuaries. A longer period of fine weather maybe also be required than just for the day of the flights, if ground based sampling (ie. vegetation sample collection) takes several additional days requiring near constant conditions.

7.6 Coordination of Fieldwork & Flights

Having been notified of a successful proposal for use of the ARS Facility the Principal Investigator will be contacted by the ARS Coordinator to discuss and confirm the user requirements for flights and sensor setup. If simultaneous fieldwork is planned the ARS coordinator will arrange with the user for a means of communication leading up to and on the day of the flight to confirm the go ahead for the mission and if possible to obtain an up to date local weather forecast from the team on the ground. The ARS coordinator has the overall responsibility of fitting in all the required campaign missions in the most efficient way and this often involves decisions, mainly based on local weather conditions, to fly in one part of the country or another where conditions may be better. Unless restricted to a specific date and time for flights when, for example, they are simultaneous with a satellite overpass, the fieldwork team should make themselves available for several days either side of the intended flight day to improve the overall chances of a successful flight.

It may be possible to set up a communications link with the ARS Coordinator / navigator via mobile phone or VHF radio to use on the day of flights. Some projects, involving coordinated field work measurements, may need to be informed by radio that a flightline is about to be flown so that simultaneous measurements can be made. Even without these communication aids, it is often possible to see the NERC aircraft during overflights, particularly at altitudes below 5,000ft, or hear the engines when at its maximum operational altitude (~10,000ft).

7.7 Ground / Auxiliary Measurements

Many users of airborne remotely sensed data who are developing applications, or testing

algorithms to derive biophysical parameters, carry out fieldwork to collect a wide variety of validation data via in-situ measurements or by sample collection for later analysis. This section relates only to the ground and auxiliary measurements that can be carried out during, or as close in time as possible to, the over flights to enhance the use and interpretation of the remotely sensed data. These measurements are mainly restricted to the acquisition of downwelling solar irradiance, upwelling radiance or surface reflectance from bright and dark targets that will be contained within the imagery, using the type of multi-band radiometers or spectroradiometers that can be obtained on loan from the NERC Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (NERC-EPFS). These data can be used in empirical corrections of the airborne data to remove or minimise the effects of atmospheric distortions or to check parametric atmospheric corrections using radiative transfer codes. More sophisticated instruments can be used to retrieve a measure of various atmospheric optical properties for direct input to radiative transfer codes, but these are not generally available to the user community. Simple measures of surface barometric pressure, temperature and humidity are also extremely useful when applying corrections to airborne remotely sensed data. (See Chapter 9)

A completely different set of measurements may also be made before, during or after the flights to determine the exact location of Ground Control Points (GCPs), use of which will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 10. These are best made with a Global Positioning Satellite (GPS) system used in differential mode to obtain precise location coordinates of features that can be easily located in the imagery. GPS-based ground control points may be used where very high precision geometric rectification is required by elimination of residual translational errors resulting from use of the in-flight navigational data. GCPs derived from map coordinates alone may not be sufficiently accurate for use due to errors in the original base map triangulation or in the transformations needed between the Ordnance Survey (OSGB36) coordinate system and the World Geodetic System (WGS84) used by the constellation of Global Positioning Satellites.

8. DATA PROCESSING STRATEGY

8.1 Overview of Data Processing

Data collected by the IDS/ATM system are downloaded from the aircraft's removable 4Gb HDs onto DAT tapes at the aircraft base in Coventry at the completion of a day's mission or prior to their reuse. Two 4Gb HD winchesters can be mounted in the aircraft and a spare held in reserve to swap over if downloading has not been completed before the next mission. Loaded winchester disks may contain ATM imagery from several flightlines and more than one PI's test site plus coincident timing/navigation data . If ATM imagery is not required for a particular proposal the IDS system is still used to record the timing synchronization and navigation data for correction of the *casi* data which is recorded separately on high density EXAbyte tapes.

Previously, data from the Daedalus 1268, recorded in-flight on a 1 inch wide High Density Digital Tape (HDDT) drive, has been transcribed to 0.5 inch wide 9-track Computer Compatible Tape (CCT) for distribution to users. No processing of the digital numbers (DN) was made and users had to apply a radiometric calibration based on a supplied sensitivity sheet containing calibration coefficients for calculation of the gain and base for each of the channels, at each of the possible gain-settings of the sensor. Although data has always been supplied on CCTs there have been three different tape formats for reading the Daedalus 1268 data (1982, 1983, and 1984 onwards). *CASI* data, acquired by NERC during test flights in 1989 and during hire from contractors in 1990 and 1991, has been supplied in various formats and with varying degrees of radiometric calibration applied. With the purchase of the Daedalus 1268, previously used under hire, and a new *casi* by the NERC, it was proposed that this was the appropriate time to implement a complete end-to-end data processing strategy which could be applied to both sensor data, to form standardized data products of consistent quality, and use a standard data format for distribution on a widely available data media.

8.2 Standard Data Products

To provide a consistent framework for the end-to-end data processing strategy a standard family of data products based on the NASA definitions (Table 8.1) has been implemented. The table and data flow, illustrated in Figure 8.1, show the elements of a complete data processing chain taking raw data, acquired by a sensor (Level 0), through a series of standard processing steps. These steps include the production of radiometrically calibrated data (Level 1b), traceable to a national standard, and derived geophysical data products (Level 2), which may follow the application of an atmospheric correction. Finally a geometric rectification to a georeferenced coordinate system or map projection can be applied using either sensor

attitude/position information alone (Level 3a) or augmented by user defined Ground Control Points (GCPs) (Level 3b). The spatially registered data set, containing the original sensor bands or, more generally, some derived data product (ie. ocean chlorophyll distribution, vegetation red-edge parameter, or surface temperature) can now be combined with other spatially referenced information to former higher level products (Level 4) such as through time series analysis.

Table 8.1. Standard data product definitions (after NASA).

Product	Definition
Level 0	- Raw "sensor format" data at original resolution.
Level 1a	- Level 0 data reformatted to image files with ancillary files appended.
Level 1b	- Level 1a data to which radiometric calibration algorithms have been applied, to produce radiance or irradiance, and to which location and navigational information has been appended.
Level 2	- Geophysical or environmental parameters derived from Level 1a or 1b data, may include atmospheric correction.
Level 3a	- Level 1b or 2 data mapped to a geographic co-ordinate system using on-board attitude and positional information only.
Level 3b	- Level 1b or 2 data mapped to a geographic co-ordinate system using on-board attitude and positional information with additional ground control points.
Level 4	- Multi-temporal/ multi-sensor gridded data products.

Within the current scope of the ARS Facility, development will be concentrated on providing a reliable radiometric calibration of both the IDS/ATM and *casi* data using the appropriate, laboratory derived, calibration coefficients (Chapter 9). This emphasis also applies to decoding and processing of the on-board and base station navigational data to derive attitude and position information on a scanline by scanline basis which will be appended to the Level 1b data product. The Level 1b data product for each flightline of each sensor will be the main data product generated by the facility. The facility will also have the capability to apply the navigation information by resampling Level 1b (or Level 2 type) data to a specified map projection, at a specified output pixel spatial resolution, using a choice of resampling algorithm (Chapter 10). The data processing facility's requirement for fast, fully automated, throughput of flightline processing and desire for standardized product archiving precludes the adoption of user specified options for the geometric rectification within the processing facility. A default

Figure 8.1 Schematic diagram of the ground-based data processing strategy.

geometrically corrected (Level 3a) data product will be generated on a standard British National Grid (BNG) map projection using predefined transformations from the GPS-based WGS84 coordinate system. This product will be generated at the recorded sensor spatial resolution, using the default resampling kernel. The default Level 3a product will be supplied to users along with the Level 1b data product as a useful indication of the geometric rectification and orientation of the georeferenced flightline. To enable the user to reproduce the geometric correction of their Level 1b data product with their own choice of map projection, output pixel size and resampling algorithm, the geometric correction software will be made available by NERC as a SUN UNIX-based executable program to valid users of the NERC ARS data. This strategy also enables the important concept of allowing the geometric correction to be carried out after any user implemented geophysical data algorithms, including any atmospheric corrections, are applied to the data. This will usually result in a reduction in the number of channels or bands of data from that of the original sensor to those of the data product (ie. a 14 channel *casi* image to a single chlorophyll density map) and thus significantly reduce the processing time for geometric correction. The user is also more likely to have the local base maps and field collected Ground Control Points (GCPs) required to derive the optional precision (Level 3b) data product.

8.3 Standard Data Format

All the data products from either the IDS/ATM or *casi* sensor will be generated in a single standard data format. The Hierarchical Data Format or HDF is a format definition standard designed to facilitate the exchange of scientific data across a range of computer platforms and was developed by the National Centre for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) at the University of Illinois. It is a particularly flexible (self-describing) and versatile data format standard, ideally suited to defining the structure of datasets combining image data and ancillary text based information. The first international application in remote sensing will be the distribution of SeaWiFS ocean colour data by NASA and an announcement has already been made that future satellite data derived from sensors within the NASA Earth Observing System (EOS) will also be distributed in HDF. To ease the transition to "yet another data format" the NERC will be providing free access to software for a variety of computer platforms to browse the header information and to extract the image data into either a standard Band Sequential (BSQ) image file or into an ERDAS Imagine file format. Further information on the HDF specification and header variables generated by the ARS Facility are contained in Appendix C. An advantage of HDF is that it is no longer necessary to indicate a specific byte location and byte length to decode a particular parameter of interest. The browse tool provides a list of all parameters available within the HDF dataset and extracts, transparently to the user, the relevant information on request.

To enable the widest dissemination and easiest access to NERC ARS data, the HDF formatted data products will be recorded and distributed on CD-ROMs which can be read on any basic CD-ROM reader attached to either mainframe, workstation or personal computer. This allows

up to 600Mb of data to be recorded on each CD-ROM, with one HDF file per data product per flightline up to the total capacity of the disk. In most cases a single CD-ROM will be more than sufficient to contain a single PI's entire data set.

It is intended at some future date to enable the re-processing of older ATM archive data, through the ground data processing system, to derive an equivalent Level 1b data with the appropriate radiometric calibration applied. It will, however, be impossible to generate the ancillary navigation information required for the geometric rectification process if this was not originally recorded (pre-July 1994).

9. RADIOMETRIC CALIBRATION

9.1 *Introduction to Radiometric Calibration*

9.2 *Corrections Applied*

9.3 *Introduction to Atmospheric Correction*

To be published shortly

10. GEOMETRIC RECTIFICATION

10.1 Introduction to geometric correction

10.2 Attitude / position navigation

10.3 Corrections applied

10.4 GCPs

10.5 Map projections & WGS84

10.6 Resampling

10.7 DEMs

To be published shortly

APPENDIX A

NERC Scientific Services Responsive Mode Services The Airborne Remote Sensing Facility

MISSION STATEMENT

- To provide airborne remotely sensed data to environmental scientists in support of their research and survey/monitoring programmes and to promote awareness and application of airborne remote sensing techniques by dissemination to the wider scientific community. By carrying out its mission it is expected that the NERC Airborne Remote sensing Facility will contribute to an improvement in the United Kingdom's industrial competitiveness and quality of life..

In order to achieve its mission the ARS Facility will:

- maintain a serviceable aircraft and modern remote sensing equipment compatible with the user requirements and make this equipment available to environmental scientists in support of their research and survey programmes;
- organise and deploy this facility and supply data to the customer as required;
- maintain and calibrate the equipment to standards required by the user community;
- maintain a core of appropriate documentation and data processing software, eg. geometric registration;
- maintain an awareness of and evaluate developments in novel technology, including the flying of innovative instrumentation;
- maintain an awareness of the user's real requirements and monitor their satisfaction with the service provided.
- seek commissioned work to supplement income to provide the required service.

User Communities:

The NSS Airborne Remote Sensing Facility exists, primarily, to provide specialist data services to the Environmental Sciences community supporting Council's remit to promote and support high quality research thereby meeting the needs of the User Communities identified in the NERC Mission. This Facility service is of direct relevance to Water, Construction, Process, Hydrocarbons, Minerals, Forestry, Agriculture, Fishing and Remote Sensing Industries together with Natural Conservation and other Regulatory Agencies and Government Departments.

NSS
January 1995

Remit and Terms of Reference For The NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Steering Committee (ARSFSC)

REMIT

The NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Steering Committee exists to:

- review applications for use of the Airborne Remote sensing Facility;
- monitor outputs from the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility;
- provide advice to Director NSS on aspects of the operations of the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility.

Director NSS, in turn, provides advice to the Science and Technology Boards of Council on Services and Facilities relevant to their remit.

Terms of Reference

1. To review applications and establish priorities, for the Head of the Facility, for the allocation of those of the Facility's resources funded from the NSS science budget, taking into account recommendations made through the NERC peer review mechanisms.
2. To review the scientific quality of work undertaken by users utilising the Facility, based on reports and publications.
3. To monitor the level of user satisfaction with the service and to analyse the user base.
4. To give guidance to the Head of the Facility on improvement of the Facility's equipment and on its service function.
5. To advise Director NSS on:
 - a) the level and direction of the internal R&D programme for the Facility.
 - b) anticipated changes in requirements from the Facility and the anticipated levels of future demand for the Facility.
6. To receive annually a report from the Head of Facility.
7. To report annually to the Director NSS and to provide advice at other times as appropriate.

Membership constraints

Membership of the Committee will be decided by Director NSS with advice from the appropriate Science and Technology Boards and suggestions from the Committee itself. It will include the Head of Facility and a representative from NSS HQ.

Members, other than ex-officio members, will be invited to serve for a term of up to four years with a maximum extension of a further two years. The Chairman will serve a maximum of four years.

NERC AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY STEERING COMMITTEE

MEMBERSHIP (at October 1997)

Prof M Barnsley (Chairman) 1/95	Department of Geography University College Swansea Singleton Park Swansea SA2 8PP	E-mail: Tel: Fax:	M.Barnsley@swan.ac.uk 01792 205678 01792 295955
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Dr L Kay	NSS Swindon	E-mail: Tel:	RLFK@nss.nerc.ac.uk 01793 411600
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Dr K Morris 11/96	Plymouth Marine Laboratory Prospect Place West Hoe Plymouth PL1 3DH	E-mail: Tel:	kpm@pml.ac.uk 01752 633408
Dr E O'Connor 1/95	British Geological Survey Knicker Hill Keyworth Nottingham NG12 5GG	E-mail: Tel:	e.connor@bgs.ac.uk 0115 9363416
Mr A Wilson 11/93	Section for Earth Observation Inst. Terrestrial Ecology Monks Wood Abbots Ripton Huntingdon Cambs PE17 2LS	E-mail: Tel:	a.wilson@nss.nerc.ac.uk 01487 773381

SECRETARY

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Mr S Groom	Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service PML Plymouth	E-mail: Tel: Fax:	s.groom@nss.nerc.ac.uk 01752 633150 01752 633101

NSS ARS Proposal Form and Guidance Notes

The following pages contain the NERC Scientific Services FY1996/97 Airborne Remote Sensing proposal application form and guidance notes.

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL
NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

AIRBORNE
REMOTE
SENSING
FACILITY

For office use only

Application No : 96/
Received :
Confirmation of receipt :

PROPOSAL APPLICATION FORM FY1996/97

Complete (pages 1-7 inclusive) and return by 1st October 1995 to: Mrs S Day
NERC Scientific Services
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU

PLEASE TYPE OR WRITE LEGIBLY THROUGHOUT

1. Principal Investigator: _____

Affiliation/Address: _____

Tel No: _____ Fax No: _____ E-mail: _____

Collaborator(s): _____

Affiliation/Address: _____

Tel No: _____ Fax No: _____ E-mail: _____

2. Title of Project: _____

NB. A typed scientific case and methodology, plus A4 sized flightplan map(s) to be attached.

3. Is this project in support of Research Council-funded research?

Please tick as appropriate :

NERC EPSRC BBSRC ESRC PPARC

4. Is this application in association with a research grant, studentship, special topic?

If so, please provide the reference no. and the name of the principal investigator.

5. Is this Project part of a NERC Thematic/Core/or Other Programme?

Please tick as appropriate:

Thematic Core Other None

Title of Programme: _____

6. Other Source of funding for this project:

If Commissioned, state Agency: _____

7. Name of Site Location: _____

Co-ordinates (Lat/Long or BNG): _____

Is this a Community Site: _____

8. Sensor(s) Required (please tick indicating choice(s) and alternative(s)).

(For each sensor requested, please complete appropriate section on following pages).

8.1 COMPACT AIRBORNE SPECTROGRAPHIC IMAGER (CASI): _____

8.2 DAEDALUS 1268 AIRBORNE THEMATIC MAPPER (ATM) _____

8.3 WILD RC-10 SURVEY CAMERA (RC-10) _____

See User Guide for more information.

8.4 Other(s) (NB: Requires full justification of choice): _____

9. Date or Months of overflight(s)

Preferred: _____

Acceptable: _____

10. Time of day

Preferred: _____

Acceptable: _____

11. Flight direction

Preferred: _____

Acceptable: _____

12. Weather quality (eg cloud cover) for data collection

Preferred: _____

Acceptable: _____

13. Are there special timing needs? (Multi-date/time, satellite overpass, tidal state):
Please provide brief details and attach details of crop cycle/harvest times, satellite overpass calendar, tide tables etc as appropriate.

14. Field work plans (include approx dates if possible)

Simultaneous: _____

Before: _____

After: _____

15. Ground Equipment:

What ground instruments will be used: _____

Will NERC EPFS spectroradiometers/GPS equipment be required? Yes/No

This is preliminary information for the EPFS management, a separate loan application will need to be made to the EPFS for any equipment.

16. Data will be provided as radiometrically and geometrically corrected data products (Level 1b and 3a, respectively). The data will be distributed on CD-ROMs in the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF). See the accompanying User Guide for further information.

NERC is only able to provide data on CD-ROMS. If other media are required then transcription arrangements and costs are the responsibility of the applicant.

17. Signatures of Principal Investigator and Head of Department in support of the application:

Principal Investigator: _____

Date: _____

Head of Department: _____

Date: _____

COMPACT AIRBORNE SPECTROGRAPHIC IMAGER (CASI)

Spatial Mode: (Max. 18 bands, full 512 spatial pixels across swath)

1a. Default Bandset (Vegetation, SeaWiFS/Ocean Colour) See User Guide

or

1b. User-defined Bandset (User _1, etc.) Use casi spectral wavelength table in User Guide

Specify	Wavelength (nm)		or	Channel number (0-287)	
Band No	Start	End		Start	End
	aaa.aa	-		bbb.bb	

- Band 1
- Band 2
- Band 3
- Band 4
- Band 5
- Band 6
- Band 7
- Band 8
- Band 9
- Band 10
- Band 11
- Band 12
- Band 13
- Band 14

-
- Band 15
 - Band 16
 - Band 17
 - Band 18
 - Band 19 Reserved for frame-shift smear data

NB: More than 14 bands may only be possible at very low spatial resolution/high flight altitudes.

For each spatial mode flight line (if different) please specify either:-

2a. Spatial resolution/pixel size (metres):

or

2b. Altitude (metres):

Spectral Mode: (Full 288 spectral channels in 39 look directions across swath, plus single spatial channel for scene recovery)

3. Scene Recovery Channel (Channel number (0-287) or Centre wavelength (nm):

4. Spread of 39 look directions (min. of 4, max. of 12):

For each spectral mode flight line (if different) please specify either:

5a. Spatial resolution (metres):

or

5b. Altitude (metres):

Enhanced Spectral Mode: (Full 288 spectral channels in central block of 101 adjacent pixels, plus single spatial channel for scene recovery). (May not be possible at high spatial resolution/low flight altitudes)

For each spectral mode flight line (if different) please specify either

6a. Spatial resolution/pixel size (metres):

or

6b. Altitude (metres):

General

7. State priority target for setting of radiometric sensitivity, ie. water or land targets:

measures downwelling solar irradiance at the same spectral
The NERC CASI has an Incident Light Sensor (ILS) which or spatial channels as those which the CASI is recording. ILS data may be used to infer the state of the atmosphere for use in atmospheric correction and retrieval of surface reflectance.

NB: If a combination of sensor(s) and camera are requested for simultaneous acquisition then a compromise on flying altitude/spatial resolution/photographic scale etc, will have to be made since the FOV of each instrument is different.

DAEDALUS 1268 ATM (11 Channel Multi-Spectral Scanner)

For each flight line (if different) please specify either

1a. Spatial resolution/pixel size (metres):

or

1b. Altitude (metres):

The enhanced ATM has an increased sensitivity range by use of 16 bit A/D conversion, eliminating the need for gain-settings and prioritising of land or water targets in the scene. There is no longer a 12th channel providing thermal data at half the gain of channel 11.

2. Blackbody temperature settings BB1, BB2 (leave blank for defaults):

BB1 = °C

BB2 = °C

(BB1 and BB2 generally bracket min and max temperature in scene)

NB: If a combination of sensor(s) and camera are requested for simultaneous acquisition then a compromise on flying altitude/spatial resolution/photographic scale etc will have to be made since the FOV of each instrument is different.

WILD RC-10 SURVEY CAMERA

- 1. Type of film (B&W, Colour, False Colour Infrared):

- 2. Basic (10%) or Stereo (60% forward) overlap (default is Basic): Basic/Stereo
If different for each flight line please specify:

- 3a. Photographic scale if required (1:10,000 etc): 1:
(Where altitude required will be (metres) = focal length (metres)/ (1/scale)

or

- 3b Altitude (metres): metres
(Where photographic scale will be (1/scale) = focal length (metres)/altitude (metres)

(Focal length of Wild RC-10 camera lens (metres) = 0.15m)

NB. If a combination of sensor(s) and camera are requested for simultaneous acquisition then a compromise on flying altitude/spatial/resolution/photographic scale etc, will have to be made since the FOV of each instrument is different.

THIS APPLICATION FORM TOGETHER WITH THE ATTACHED SCIENTIFIC CASE AND FLIGHT MAPS MUST BE RETURNED TO MRS S DAY AT NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES, POLARIS HOUSE, NORTH STAR AVENUE, SWINDON, SN2 1EU BY 1ST OCTOBER 1995.

Please complete your part of the following acknowledgement slip which will be returned to you on receipt of your application.

Name: _____

Affiliation/Address: _____

We confirm receipt of your Proposal Application for use of the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility.

Ref No: 96/

Signature: _____

Date _____

**NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES
AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY
GUIDANCE NOTES FOR THE PROPOSAL APPLICATION FORM**

ITEM 1: Please note that if a student is making an application it is necessary for his supervisor to be nominated as the Principal Investigator.

ITEM 2: A Scientific case in support of the proposal must be attached. General research statements are not appropriate. Proposals should make specific reference to the benefits the principal investigator will get from using ARS facility data together, with explicit statements as to how the scientist will use and process ATM/CASI/ air photography. The scientific case - maximum 5 pages excluding map(s) - should specifically address the following items:-

How airborne remote sensing will benefit the Research.
Methodology - particularly with regard to the data processing and application of the airborne data.

Applicants should also enclose on a separate sheet a bibliography of any papers, theses and presentations which derive from previous NERC airborne remote sensing programmes.

NB: It should be noted that the review panel will take into account the publication record of those who have already acquired data from previous NERC airborne remote sensing programmes and strongly recommend the publication of work in peer reviewed journals.

Applicants should also enclose an A4 size map of the site location, preferably taken from an Ordnance Survey map. (1:50,000 or 1:25,000) and clearly showing the flightline(s) and areas of special importance to the project.

ITEM 6: If this is a Commissioned project, the name of the funding agency should be provided and details on its involvement in the project provided in the attached text.

NB. Applicants should be advised that any project related to providing information to a third party, for example another Government or public agency, or private company will not be supported unless that agency/company makes a significant contribution to the costs of data acquisition. Data acquired during the NERC airborne remote sensing campaigns remains NERC property and the data may not be divulged to a third party, except through the open literature, without prior consent from NERC.

ITEM 7: Please provide identifying site name and location.

The use of a community site will be favoured in the context of providing ground support equipment and in flying operations. A community site would be represented by a set of multiple applications, based at one site, where the remote sensing data could be shared to address a number of disciplines or an interdisciplinary project aimed at addressing a major research objective.

ITEM 8: Please see the relevant section on the individual sensor specifications. Applicants should consider carefully the volume of data which their proposal will generate - particularly in the context of the resources (time and money) to process, analyse and present results from the full data set.

Airborne sensors, other than those offered, may be available via short term hire if a sufficient scientific case can be made in order to provide novel or complementary data. However the availability of such additional sensors - unless freely available - will be subject to budgetary resources.

- ITEMS 9
10:** Please be as flexible as possible on timings. A severe time constraint will reduce the chance of the site being flown - particularly in the context of prevailing good weather conditions.
- ITEM 11:** Please provide a heading (eg 90° (due East)) for each of the flightlines, but be aware of the likely position of the sun at the time of day you have requested for data acquisition. Flying into or away from the solar azimuth minimises any atmospheric distortions and makes them symmetrical across the scan and also reduces sunglint over aquatic targets.
- ITEM 12:** Please enter in the space provided a description of the preferred or acceptable weather/cloud conditions etc. Completely blue sky, some fraction of cloud cover or completely overcast, no haze or slight haze acceptable, etc.
- ITEM 13:** Where there are special timing needs supply crop cycle/harvest times, satellite overpass calendars or tide tables along with the scientific case. Please state, if known, if there are any restrictions on flying at the site eg. altitude, day of the week, restricted airspace etc.
- ITEM 14:** Provide approximate dates if possible for associated field work.
- ITEM15:** Applicants who are requesting access to equipment from the NERC Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (EPFS) will need to complete a separate application form.
- ITEM16:** Data from the CASI and Daedalus (ATM) systems will be produced at various levels of processing within the NASA defined family of standard data products (see User Guide). Those levels available at present are:

Level 0 - Raw uncalibrated data. (Not normally provided to applications users).

Level 1b - Radiometrically calibrated data in radiance units. All relative calibration distortions caused by the sensor optical/electronic characteristics have been removed. Absolute calibration is traceable to a national standard. Navigation data is appended to allow geometric correction by the user.

Level 3a - Geometrically corrected data. This provides data corrected for the attitude changes of the platform and viewing geometry of the sensor based on platform and sensor ephemeris only.

Further geocoding of Level 1b data or user generated geophysical data products (Level 2) can be accomplished by use of a SUN unix-based software package available from the NERC exclusively for the period and purpose of the NERC supported analyses. The software will enable the user to input Ground Control Points (GCPs) and allow control over the output map projection, output pixel size and resampling method.

Data as both Level 1b and 3a products will be provided to users on CD-ROM(s) using the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF) to hold all image and ancillary data for each sensor flightline or complete mission/project (max. capacity 600Mb). Software to read the CD-ROMs on to a number of hardware platforms will be made available from NERC. Please contact Mrs Angela Morrison for details on such system availability.

Mrs A Morrison: Tel: 0793 411555
 Fax: 0793 411959
 Email: A.Morrison@nss.nerc.ac.uk

- ITEM17:** The signature of the Principal Investigator must be supplied. It is also necessary for the Head of Department to sign the application form thereby indicating his knowledge of and support for the proposal.

User Quality Check Questionnaire

The following pages contain the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing User Quality Check Questionnaire to be completed by all users of data from the ARS Facility and returned within three months of receiving their data.

ATM DATA

NERC AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING PROGRAMME 1995/96 CUSTOMER QUALITY CHECK

This form must be completed and returned to NERC Scientific Services within 3 months of receipt of the data. Failure to do so will undoubtedly incur future restraints on data provision.

1. Site/Principal Investigator

Site Name:

Site Ref No: Acquisition Date(s).....

Principal Investigator:

Address:

Tel: Fax: Email:

2. CD-ROM Quality

Please tick if CD-ROM shows:

Damage in any way (please specify below)

.....

.....

3. Data Quality

Please tick if data shows:

Errors in data (eg parity errors)

Missing bands

Data drop-outs

Saturation

Other faults (please specify below)

.....

.....

4. Data Coverage

Does data comply with proposal request and/or subsequent agreement with NERC operations staff?

Yes

No

☐	☐	Is area coverage OK?
☐	☐	Are flight directions OK?
☐	☐	Is altitude/resolution OK?
☐	☐	Is time of day/time of year OK?

If 'NO' box ticked, please give further details of problem.

.....

.....

PTO

5. Enclosures

Please tick what you have received:

- CD-ROMs
- Site plan
- Air photography B/W Colour Infra-red
- Prints Negatives
- NSS Airborne Remote Sensing Handbook (new users)
- Delivery Note

Is there any other supplementary information that would assist you? Please specify.

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6. Any Additional Comments

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7. Please assess your overall satisfaction with the data supplied on the following basis

- 10 - 8 Very satisfied
- 7 - 4 Satisfied
- 3 - 1 Dissatisfied
- 0 Do not have an opinion

Overall assessment:

Please return this form **WITHIN 3 MONTHS OF RECEIPT OF ENCLOSED DATA** to:

Mrs S Day
 NERC Scientific Services
 Polaris House
 North Star Avenue
 Swindon
 Wilts
 SN2 1EU

CASI DATA

NERC AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING PROGRAMME 1995/96 CUSTOMER QUALITY CHECK

This form must be completed and returned to NERC Scientific Services within 3 months or receipt of the data. Failure to do so will undoubtedly incur future restraints on data provision.

1. Site/Principal Investigator

Site Name:

Site Ref No: Acquisition Date(s).....

Principal Investigator:

Address:

Tel: Fax: Email:

2. CD-ROM Quality

Please tick if CD-ROM shows:

Damage in any way (please specify below)

.....
.....

3. Data Quality

Please tick if data shows:

Errors in data (eg parity errors)

Missing bands

Data drop-outs

Saturation

Other faults (please specify below)

.....
.....

4. Data Coverage

Does data comply with proposal request and/or subsequent agreement with NERC operations staff?

Yes

No

Is area coverage OK?
 Are flight directions OK?
 Is altitude/resolution OK?
 Is time of day/time of year OK?

If 'NO' box ticked, please give further details of problem.

.....
.....

PTO

5. Enclosures

Please tick what you have received:

- CD-ROMs
- Site plan
- Air photography B/W Colour Infra-red
- Prints Negatives
- Airborne Remote Sensing Handbook (new users)
- Delivery Note

Is there any other supplementary information that would assist you? Please specify.

.....
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6. Any Additional Comments

.....
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.....
.....

7. Please assess your overall satisfaction with the data supplied on the following basis

- 10 - 8 Very satisfied
- 7 - 4 Satisfied
- 3 - 1 Dissatisfied
- 0 Do not have an opinion

Overall assessment:

Please return this form **WITHIN 3 MONTHS OF RECEIPT OF ENCLOSED DATA** to:

Mrs S Day
NERC Scientific Services
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wilts
SN2 1EU

PHOTOGRAPHIC DATA ONLY

NERC AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING FACILITY AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING PROGRAMME 1995/96 CUSTOMER QUALITY CHECK

This form must be completed and returned to NERC Scientific Services within 3 months or receipt of the data. Failure to do so will undoubtedly incur future restraints on data provision.

1. Site/Principal Investigator

Site Name:

Site Ref No: Acquisition Date(s).....

Principal Investigator:

Address:

Tel: Fax: Email:

2. Data Quality - Air Photography

Please tick (and supply details) if air photography shows:

- Incomplete site coverage
- Wrong scale
- Incorrect forward overlap (stereo)
- Wrong film type (eg B/W, Colour, Infra-red)
- Wrong media (eg prints, dia positives, negatives)

Please give further details fo problem

.....
.....

3. Any Additional Comments

.....
.....
.....

4. Enclosures

Please tick what you have received:

- Site plan
- Air photography B/W Colour Infra-red
- Prints Negatives
- NSS Airborne Remote Sensing Handbook (new users)
- Delivery note

Is there any other supplementary information that would assist you? Please specify.

.....

PTO

5. Please assess your overall satisfaction with the data supplied on the following basis

- 10 - 8 Very satisfied
- 7 - 4 Satisfied
- 3 - 1 Dissatisfied
- 0 Do not have an opinion

Overall assessment:

Please return this form **WITHIN 3 MONTHS OF RECEIPT OF ENCLOSED DATA** to:

Mrs S Day
NERC Scientific Services
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wilts SN2 1EU

APPENDIX B

Sensor Characteristics

ATM Bandset

Band	Centre/Width (nm)	Start nm	End nm	Landsat TM Bands	Purpose
1.	435 30	420	- 450		Water penetration, mapping
2.	485 70	450	- 520	1	Water, soil/veg discrimination
3.	560 80	520	- 600	2	Peak of green veg reflectance
4.	615 20	605	- 625		Water quality,dissolved matter
5.	660 60	630	- 690	3	Max chlorophyll absorption
6.	722.5 55	695	- 750		Vegetation red-edge curve
7.	830 140	760	- 900	4	Vegetation max reflectance
8.	980 140	910	- 1050		NIR including water absorp
9	1650 200	1550	- 1750	5	Soil/Veg moisture
10.	2215 270	2080	- 2350	7	Rock discrimination
11.	10750 4500	8500	- 13000	6§	Surface temperature, moisture

§ Thermal band broadened for aircraft operation.

ATM Calibration

Dates of laboratory calibration

Calibration	Date	Comments
ATM070394	07/03/94	Panel calibration by EPFS
ATM020894	02/08/94	
ATM020894	06/12/94	Reduced sensitivity coefficients
	~~~~~	Scan-mirror re-silvering
ATM290795	29/07/95	Panel calibration by EPFS (31/07/95)

Current radiometric calibration of the original Daedalus 1268, as used in the Interim Solution, is based on a laboratory calibration procedure using a Daedalus AB532 test bench. Light from two halogen lamps is reflected off a barium sulphate panel into the scan-head illuminating the central pixels of a scan line. Measurements taken with the lamps on and off are used to determine the gain and offset for each band under the various sensor gain-settings using a knowledge of the lamp/panel spectral light output. Periodically the lamp/panel output is checked by intercalibration with a spectroradiometer from the NERC-EPFS that is traceable to a national standard. The exact spectral calibration of the NERC ATM has yet to be determined, but the following spectral response curves have been derived from a similar Daedalus 1268 scanner.

Spectral Response of Daedalus 1268 Visible and NIR channels



**Spectral Response of Daedalus 1268 SWIR channels**



## CASI Calibration

### Dates of laboratory calibration

Calibration	Date	Comments
NERCCAL1	11/04/94 - 14/04/94	
NERCCAL2	24/08/94 - 26/08/94	Spectral calibration not available
ITCAL3A	21/11/94 - 23/11/94	SHU 303 sensor head with 502 ICU
NERCCAL4	23/11/94 - 25/11/94	
NERCCAL5	15/03/95 - 17/03/95	Calibration not valid due to low light input
NERCCAL6	26/04/95 - 28/04/95	

#### NERCCAL1

G0 = 915.01633983

G1 = -1.8216215493

G2 = 9.6651998977 E-5

G3 = 3.7088417157 E-8

#### NERCCAL4

G0 = 915.1402331455

G1 = -1.815971752

G2 = 3.7158712754 E-5

G3 = 2.0846832222 E-7

#### NERCCAL5

G0 = 911.6932276114

G1 = -1.8380054923

G2 = 2.5315083474 E-4

G3 = -3.6265892667 E-7

#### NERCCAL6

G0 = 911.67433412

G1 = -1.8370377163

G2 = 2.6997881474 E-4

G3 = -4.6539492438 E-7

The centre wavelength of each detector element can be calculated using the following equation, using the above G numbers supplied from the appropriate laboratory calibration.

$$\lambda = G0 + R \cdot G1 + R^2 \cdot G2 + R^3 \cdot G3$$

where  $\lambda$  is the centre wavelength in nanometres (nm) and R is the detector number (0-287).

*CASI* spectral bandwidths associated with each detector element can be calculated using the following equation, using the supplied  $a_0$  to  $a_5$  coefficients.

$$BW(\lambda) = \sum a_i \lambda^i \quad (\text{for } i = 0 \text{ to } 5)$$

where,  $BW(\lambda)$  is the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) spectral bandwidth (nm),  $\lambda$  is the centre wavelength (nm) and  $a_0$  to  $a_5$  are:

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= -2.309 \text{ E}+2 \\ a_1 &= +1.3342 \text{ E}+0 \\ a_2 &= -3.1068 \text{ E}-3 \\ a_3 &= +3.0701 \text{ E}-6 \\ a_4 &= -1.0579 \text{ E}-9 \\ a_5 &= -3.0166 \text{ E}-14 \end{aligned}$$

This relationship has an accuracy of  $\pm 0.1$ nm. The shape of the pixel-slit spectral band distribution can be best approximated by a gaussian function.

The following *casi* spectral calibration table (for NERCCAL1) was calculated using the above information and was used for the construction of the example default vegetation and SeaWiFS / ocean colour bandsets.

## CASI Spectral Calibration Tables - NERCCAL1

CCD. row	Centre (nm)	Bdwidth (nm)	CCD. row	Centre (nm)	Bdwidth (nm)	CCD. row	Centre (nm)	Bdwidth (nm)
0	915.02	7.62	48	827.81	5.45	96	741.06	3.11
1	913.19	7.59	49	825.99	5.40	97	739.26	3.08
2	911.37	7.57	50	824.18	5.34	98	737.46	3.04
3	909.55	7.54	51	822.37	5.29	99	735.66	3.01
4	907.73	7.52	52	820.56	5.23	100	733.86	2.97
5	905.91	7.49	53	818.75	5.17	101	732.06	2.94
6	904.09	7.46	54	816.94	5.12	102	730.26	2.91
7	902.27	7.43	55	815.13	5.06	103	728.46	2.88
8	900.45	7.39	56	813.32	5.01	104	726.65	2.85
9	898.63	7.36	57	811.50	4.95	105	724.85	2.82
10	896.81	7.32	58	809.69	4.90	106	723.05	2.79
11	894.99	7.29	59	807.88	4.84	107	721.25	2.76
12	893.17	7.25	60	806.08	4.79	108	719.46	2.73
13	891.35	7.21	61	804.27	4.74	109	717.66	2.71
14	889.53	7.17	62	802.46	4.68	110	715.86	2.68
15	887.71	7.13	63	800.65	4.63	111	714.06	2.66
16	885.90	7.09	64	798.84	4.57	112	712.26	2.63
17	884.08	7.05	65	797.03	4.52	113	710.46	2.61
18	882.26	7.00	66	795.22	4.47	114	708.66	2.59
19	880.44	6.96	67	793.41	4.42	115	706.86	2.57
20	878.62	6.92	68	791.60	4.36	116	705.07	2.54
21	876.81	6.87	69	789.80	4.31	117	703.27	2.52
22	874.99	6.82	70	787.99	4.26	118	701.47	2.51
23	873.17	6.78	71	786.18	4.21	119	699.67	2.49
24	871.35	6.73	72	784.37	4.16	120	697.88	2.47
25	869.54	6.68	73	782.57	4.11	121	696.08	2.45
26	867.72	6.63	74	780.76	4.06	122	694.28	2.44
27	865.90	6.58	75	778.95	4.01	123	692.49	2.42
28	864.09	6.53	76	777.15	3.96	124	690.69	2.41
29	862.27	6.48	77	775.34	3.91	125	688.90	2.39
30	860.46	6.43	78	773.54	3.87	126	687.10	2.38
31	858.64	6.38	79	771.73	3.82	127	685.31	2.37
32	856.82	6.33	80	769.92	3.77	128	683.51	2.36
33	855.01	6.27	81	768.12	3.73	129	681.72	2.35
34	853.19	6.22	82	766.31	3.68	130	679.92	2.34
35	851.38	6.17	83	764.51	3.64	131	678.13	2.33
36	849.56	6.11	84	762.70	3.59	132	676.33	2.32
37	847.75	6.06	85	760.90	3.55	133	674.54	2.32
38	845.94	6.01	86	759.10	3.51	134	672.74	2.31
39	844.12	5.95	87	757.29	3.46	135	670.95	2.30
40	842.31	5.90	88	755.49	3.42	136	669.16	2.30
41	840.49	5.84	89	753.68	3.38	137	667.36	2.30
42	838.68	5.79	90	751.88	3.34	138	665.57	2.29
43	836.87	5.73	91	750.08	3.30	139	663.78	2.29
44	835.06	5.68	92	748.27	3.26	140	661.99	2.29
45	833.24	5.62	93	746.47	3.22	141	660.19	2.29
46	831.43	5.56	94	744.67	3.19	142	658.40	2.29
47	829.62	5.51	95	742.87	3.15	143	656.61	2.29

CCD. row	Centre (nm)	Bdwidth (nm)	CCD. row	Centre (nm)	Bdwidth (nm)	CCD. row	Centre (nm)	Bdwidth (nm)
144	654.82	2.29	192	569.09	3.09	240	483.91	4.11
145	653.03	2.30	193	567.31	3.12	241	482.14	4.12
146	651.24	2.30	194	565.53	3.14	242	480.37	4.12
147	649.44	2.30	195	563.75	3.17	243	478.60	4.12
148	647.65	2.31	196	561.97	3.20	244	476.83	4.13
149	645.86	2.31	197	560.19	3.22	245	475.07	4.13
150	644.07	2.32	198	558.41	3.25	246	473.30	4.13
151	642.28	2.33	199	556.63	3.28	247	471.53	4.13
152	640.49	2.33	200	554.85	3.31	248	469.76	4.12
153	638.70	2.34	201	553.08	3.33	249	468.00	4.12
154	636.91	2.35	202	551.30	3.36	250	466.23	4.12
155	635.13	2.36	203	549.52	3.39	251	464.46	4.11
156	633.34	2.37	204	547.74	3.41	252	462.70	4.10
157	631.55	2.38	205	545.97	3.44	253	460.93	4.09
158	629.76	2.39	206	544.19	3.46	254	459.17	4.08
159	627.97	2.41	207	542.41	3.49	255	457.40	4.07
160	626.18	2.42	208	540.63	3.52	256	455.64	4.05
161	624.40	2.43	209	538.86	3.54	257	453.87	4.04
162	622.61	2.45	210	537.08	3.57	258	452.11	4.02
163	620.82	2.46	211	535.31	3.59	259	450.34	4.00
164	619.03	2.48	212	533.53	3.62	260	448.58	3.98
165	617.25	2.49	213	531.75	3.64	261	446.82	3.96
166	615.46	2.51	214	529.98	3.67	262	445.05	3.94
167	613.67	2.53	215	528.20	3.69	263	443.29	3.91
168	611.89	2.54	216	526.43	3.72	264	441.53	3.88
169	610.10	2.56	217	524.65	3.74	265	439.76	3.85
170	608.32	2.58	218	522.88	3.76	266	438.00	3.82
171	606.53	2.60	219	521.11	3.79	267	436.24	3.79
172	604.75	2.62	220	519.33	3.81	268	434.48	3.75
173	602.96	2.64	221	517.56	3.83	269	432.72	3.71
174	601.18	2.66	222	515.79	3.85	270	430.95	3.67
175	599.39	2.68	223	514.01	3.87	271	429.19	3.63
176	597.61	2.70	224	512.24	3.89	272	427.43	3.59
177	595.82	2.72	225	510.47	3.91	273	425.67	3.54
178	594.04	2.75	226	508.69	3.93	274	423.91	3.49
179	592.26	2.77	227	506.92	3.95	275	422.15	3.44
180	590.47	2.79	228	505.15	3.96	276	420.39	3.39
181	588.69	2.82	229	503.38	3.98	277	418.63	3.34
182	586.91	2.84	230	501.61	4.00	278	416.87	3.28
183	585.12	2.86	231	499.84	4.01	279	415.11	3.22
184	583.34	2.89	232	498.07	4.03	280	413.35	3.16
185	581.56	2.91	233	496.29	4.04	281	411.60	3.09
186	579.78	2.94	234	494.52	4.05	282	409.84	3.02
187	578.00	2.96	235	492.75	4.07	283	408.08	2.95
188	576.21	2.99	236	490.98	4.08	284	406.32	2.88
189	574.43	3.01	237	489.21	4.09	285	404.56	2.81
190	572.65	3.04	238	487.45	4.09	286	402.81	2.73
191	570.87	3.07	239	485.68	4.10	287	401.05	2.65

## **CASI Default Bandsets**

### **Default Vegetation Bandset**

Ch	Centre/Width (nm)	Start nm (Ch No.)	End nm (Ch No.)	Purpose
1.	450 20	441.53 (264) -	459.17 (254)	Blue veg response
2.	490 20	480.37 (242) -	499.84 (231)	Veg. response
3.	552 10	547.74 (204) -	556.63 (199)	Green veg max.
4.	670 10	665.57 (138) -	674.54 (133)	Veg Absorp max.(1)
5.	700 10	694.28 (122) -	703.27 (117)	Red-Edge (2)
6.	710 10	705.07 (116) -	711.06 (111)	Red-Edge (3)
7.	740 10	735.66 (99) -	744.67 (94)	Red-Edge (4)
8.	750 7	746.47 (93) -	753.68 (89)	Red-Edge (5)
9	762 5	760.90 (85) -	764.51 (83)	Oxygen Absorp.
10.	780 10	775.34 (77) -	784.37 (72)	Veg reflec.max. (6)
11.	820 10	815.13 (55) -	824.18 (50)	Water Absorp.
12.	865 10	860.46 (30) -	869.54 (25)	N.I.R. plateau

Channels 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 10 can be used to fit inverted gaussian for vegetation red-edge.

Channels 4, 6, 7 and 10 for Guyot-Baret red-edge model.

Channels 1, 3, 4, 10 and 12 for various vegetation indices and to simulate main satellite channels.

Channels 10, 11 and 12 for determining water vapour content for atmospheric correction at all wavelengths.

Channels 8, 9 and 10 for determining atmospheric oxygen for path-length correction of above water vapour measurements.

If fewer channels are available due to integration time / altitude conflicts then reduce bandset by deleting ch 2 (490nm), then ch 9 (762) and then ch 7 (740nm) for 11, 10 and 9 channel bandsets, respectively.

CASI Default Vegetation Bandset



## **CASI Default Bandsets**

### **Default SeaWiFS / Ocean Colour Bandset**

Ch	Centre/Width (nm)	Start nm (Ch No.)	End nm (Ch No.)	SeaWiFS Ch	Purpose
1	412 20	402.81 (286) -	422.15 (275)	1	Gelb. + Chlor.
2	443 20	432.72 (269) -	453.87 (257)	2	Chlor. + Gelb.
3	490 20	480.37 (242) -	499.84 (231)	3	Gelb. + Chlor. + Acces.
4	510 20	501.61 (230) -	519.33 (220)	4	Acces.
5	555 20	545.97 (205) -	565.53 (194)	5	Acces. + Chlor.
6	620 20	610.10 (169) -	629.76 (158)		MERIS + Acces.
7	670 20	660.19 (141) -	679.92 (130)	6	Chlor+Sed+ChlorF+R-E
8	682.5 5	681.72 (129) -	685.31 (127)		ChlorF.
9	710 10	705.07 (116) -	715.86 (110)		R-E.+ ChlorF.
10	752 15	744.76 (94) -	759.10 (86)	7a	Sed. + Aeros. + R-E.
11	762 5	760.90 (85) -	764.51 (83)		Oxygen Absorp.
12	775 20	766.31 (82) -	784.37 (72)	7b	Sed. + Aeros. + R-E.
13	820 10	815.13 (55) -	824.18 (50)		Water Vapour Absorp.
14	865 40	845.94 (38) -	884.08 (17)	8	Sed. + Aeros.

Gelb. - Gelbstoff

Acces. - Accessory Pigment

Sed. - Sediments

R-E. - Vegetation Red-Edge

Chlor. - Chlorophyll

MERIS - MERIS compatible band

ChlorF. - Chlorophyll Fluorescence

Aeros. - Aerosols

Least important band is Ch 6. at 620nm and then Ch 11. at 762nm (Can be dropped if fewer channels are necessary).

Channels 10 and 12 are both required to simulate the single SeaWiFS channel 7 due to the notch in the satellite sensor response to avoid the oxygen absorption feature.

CASI Default SeaWiFS / Ocean Colour Bandset



***APPENDIX C***  
***HDF Specification / Data Format***

**To be published shortly**